

Council for
BRITISH ARCHAEOLOGY
8 St. Andrew's Place, London, N.W.1

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21st February, 1972

Dear Andrew,

Thank you for your letter of 18th February. It looks as though I should be in my office all day on Friday, 25th February, and delighted to see you whenever you care to come along. The pottery is in my room and we could go through it together. If you like to ring up when you reach town and fix a time, that might be convenient. Alternatively I will keep the afternoon free from 2 to 4.

All good wishes,

Yours sincerely,

Andrew Williamson, Esq.,
15 St. John's Street,
Oxford.